

Multifunctional Microgel Magnetic/Optical Traps for SERS Ultradetection

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ABSTRACT: We report on the fabrication of a SERS substrate comprising magnetic and silver particles encapsulated within a poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAM) thermoresponsive microgel. This colloidal substrate has the ability to adsorb analytes from solution while it is expanded (low temperature) and reversibly generate hot spots upon collapse (high temperature or drying). Additionally, the magnetic functionality permits concentration of the composite particles into small spatial regions, which can be exploited to decrease the amount of material per analysis while improving its SERS detection limit. Proof of concept for the sequestration of uncommon molecular systems is demonstrated through the first SERS analysis of pentachlorophenol (PCP), a chlorinated ubiquitous environmental pollutant.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid, sensitive, and accurate detection is central in environmental, analytical, and bioanalytical sciences. Surface enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) spectroscopy^{1–3} is a unique ultrasensitive technique that allows for the unequivocal identification of analytes in a wide variety of matrices, with no (or very little) need for processing prior to the analysis. SERS has therefore been extensively investigated as a convenient tool for diagnosis, biodetection, and environmental monitoring.^{4–8} Notwithstanding, this technique still encompasses several limitations, one of the most restrictive ones being that only analytes with suitable functional groups (i.e., thiol, nitrile, amine, and carboxylic) provide sufficiently good signals for ultrasensitive analytical purposes in a convenient time. This is usually not a drawback when dealing with biorelated problems, as most of the biorelevant structures contain at least one of such groups.^{9,10} However, organic pollutants and other hazardous materials in environmental problems are characterized by an extraordinary diversity of chemical structures, including nonfunctionalized aliphatic and/or aromatic compounds (alcohols, ethers, ketones, halides, etc.) with no affinity for gold or silver,¹¹ the most common plasmonic materials. These molecular systems are a priori impossible to detect, via direct SERS and thus indirect approaches are required. These approaches are typically based on the surface functionalization of the plasmonic nanoparticles with different receptors, in an attempt to increase the local concentration of the molecule to be determined near the electric field generated by the particle. Examples of these strategies include electrostatic attraction by the counterions,¹² highly selective molecules such as aptamers,^{13,14} antibodies,^{15,16} or calixarenes^{17,18} and thiolated aliphatic monolayers.^{19,20} However, all of these methods are highly selective,

so that only certain molecules are effectively adsorbed to the plasmonic surface.

We have recently developed a new family of hybrid materials that are capable of mechanically trapping molecules from aqueous solution.²¹ These materials comprise a metallic core surrounded by a thermoresponsive poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAM) shell. However, while the trapping properties of these systems are clearly efficient, the formation of hot spots is completely inhibited because each single particle is isolated by the surrounding polymer shell,^{22–24} thereby restricting the detection limits. Additionally, the concept of dynamic hot spots has recently been demonstrated by incorporation of silver or gold nanoparticles within a macroscopic gel matrix,^{25,26} resulting in the generation of hot spots when the gel was dehydrated and the particles became closer to each other. This concept can in principle be applied in a similar way to microgel spheres through the incorporation of multiple nanoparticles, with the additional advantage that the microgel collapse can be externally triggered by simply increasing the temperature. Another strategy that has proven successful to lower the actual detection limits in SERS, is the addition of a magnetic functionality to the SERS colloidal platform,²⁷ which permits the rapid concentration of the plasmonic hybrid material within a small region prior to SERS analysis; thus, a small amount of the sensing platform would be required, decreasing the concentration of analyte needed to obtain a meaningful SERS signal.²⁸ It should be noted that the use of silver is expected not only to widen the spectral window of excitation as compared with gold, but also to increase the

Scheme 1. (A) Magnetite Synthesis Using a Thermal Decomposition Method; (B) pNIPAM Coating; and, (C) Silver Nucleation and Growth

enhancement factor for SERS,²⁹ which is restricted in gold to the red and the NIR because of the overlap with interband transitions.^{30,31}

In this work, we engineered and fabricated a SERS substrate comprising magnetite and silver particles encapsulated within a pNIPAM thermoresponsive shell. Additionally, proof of concept for the sequestration of uncommon molecular systems is demonstrated through the first SERS analysis of pentachlorophenol (PCP), a ubiquitous environmental pollutant extensively used as herbicide, insecticide, fungicide, algacide, and disinfectant and even as a preserver of wooden materials. Rapid and sensitive identification of PCP is extremely important as it is highly soluble (it easily contaminates tap water) and bioaccumulates in fatty tissues, so even small exposures may eventually reach dangerous levels. In fact, acute exposure results in harmful effects on the liver, kidneys, blood, lungs, nervous system, immune system, and gastrointestinal tract. Chronic effects after exposure to low levels include damage to the liver, kidneys, blood, and nervous system, as well as cancer (classified as B2 carcinogen by the EPA).³²

EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals. Ascorbic acid, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), butenoic acid, silver nitrate (AgNO_3), sodium borohydride (NaBH_4), *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM, 97%), $\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, *N*, *N'*-methylenebisacrylamide (BIS), glycine (98.5%), and pentachlorophenol (PCP) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. Iron(III) acetylacetonate (99%), undecenoic acid (99%), 2,2'-azobis(2-methylpropionamide) dihydrochloride (AAPH), dibenzyl ether (99%) and 1-naphthalenethiol (INAT) were supplied by Acros Organics. All reactants were ACS grade and used without further purification. Water was purified using a Milli-Q system (Millipore).

Synthesis of Magnetic Nanoparticles Using Undecenoic Acid.

The synthesis of the magnetic particles was performed using a slight modification of a previously reported method (Scheme 1).³³ Briefly, for the preparation of 13 nm edge length particles, 0.353 g (1 mmol) of iron(III) acetylacetonate was mixed with 0.688 g (4 mmol) of undecenoic acid in 25 mL of dibenzyl ether. After 1 h under vacuum in a Schlenk line, the solution was heated to 200 °C with a constant heating rate of 6–7 °C/min under an argon flow and vigorous stirring. After 2 h at 200 °C, the solution was heated to reflux with a constant heating rate of 5.2 °C min⁻¹ and then maintained at this temperature for one additional hour. After cooling down to room temperature, a mixture of toluene and acetone was added to the solution and then centrifuged. The precipitate was washed several times with the mixture of toluene and acetone (1:1). The particles were stored in ethanol.

pNIPAM Coating. In a 15-mL vial, 350 μL (3.7 wt %) of magnetic nanoparticles was diluted in 10 mL of water and sonicated during 15 min to remove the possible clusters due to particle aggregation. Then, the vial was immersed in a water bath at 70 °C and 80 μL of butenoic acid was added to incorporate a terminal double bond over the magnetic nanoparticles surface.³⁴ This solution was maintained at 70 °C for 1 h, and then 200 μL of CTAB 0.2 M was added to minimize aggregation during the centrifugation process and to remove excess butenoic acid. The sample was then centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 30 min. After removing the supernatant, the precipitate was diluted in 10 mL of water and sonicated during 15 min. The solution was then immersed in a water bath at 70 °C and stirred mechanically at 350 rpm under a N_2 flow. Then, 0.2264 g of NIPAM and 0.0312 g of BIS were added to the vinyl functionalized magnetic nanoparticles. After 15 min, the polymerization was initiated adding 100 μL (0.1 M) of AAPH, and after 15 additional minutes, the N_2 flow was removed and the polymerization process was maintained for 2 h. Finally, the light brown mixture was allowed to cool down to room temperature and the vial was placed on a 1.2 T neodymium permanent magnet for 24 h.

Figure 1. (A) TEM image of as prepared magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles. (B) Hysteresis loops at 5 and 300 K for the same nanoparticles. Inset: Detail of the low magnetic field region.

Thereafter, the supernatant (containing free microgel spheres) was discarded and the brown precipitate at the bottom of the vial was redispersed in 10 mL of water.

Silver Nucleation and Growth within Magnetite@pNIPAM Microgels. AgNO_3 (100 μL , 25 mM) was added under mild magnetic stirring to 10 mL of magnetite@pNIPAM hybrid particles. The mixture was kept for 30 min at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$ to allow a homogeneous diffusion of $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ ions into the gel network. Then, 300 μL of NaBH_4 10 mM was added to the sample under vigorous magnetic stirring to promote the nucleation of silver nanoparticles inside the pNIPAM microgel network.³⁵ Silver growth³⁶ was achieved by adding a mixture composed of CTAB (2.5 mL, 0.2 M), glycine at pH 9.5 (2.5 mL, 0.4 mM), and AgNO_3 (800 μL , 0.25 mM) to 5 mL of the previously prepared magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM. Then, 600 μL of ascorbic acid 100 mM was added under vigorous magnetic stirring and the mixture was maintained at 27 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min, followed by centrifugation (3500 rpm, 30 min) to remove excess ascorbic acid, and redispersion in 5 mL of water.

Characterization. UV-vis spectra were recorded using an Agilent 8453 diode array spectrophotometer. Transmission electron microscopy was carried out using a JEOL JEM 1010 microscope operating at an acceleration voltage of 100 kV. Magnetic data were recorded in a vibrating sample magnetometer (MLVSM9MagLab 9 T, Oxford Instruments). Magnetization curves were recorded at 5 K and at room temperature (300 K) by first saturating the sample in a field of 3 T; the saturation magnetization (M_s) values were evaluated by extrapolating to infinite field the experimental results obtained in the high field range where the magnetization linearly increases with $1/H$.

Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering Spectroscopy. Raman and SERS experiments were conducted in a micro-Renishaw InVia Reflex system. The spectrograph uses high resolution gratings (1800 or 1200 grooves cm^{-1} for the visible or NIR, respectively) with additional band-pass filter optics, a confocal microscope, and a 2D-CCD camera. Excitation was carried out at different energies, using laser lines at 532 (Nd:Yag), 633 (HeNe) and 785 (diode) nm. Measurements were made in a confocal microscope in backscattering geometry using a 50 \times objective with NA values of 0.75 which provided scattering areas of 1 μm^2 with accumulation times of 10 s. The power at the sample was varied between 14 mW and 0.2 mW.

For the SERS characterization of the material, 1 mL aliquots of the magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM system were stabilized at 4 $^\circ\text{C}$ (expanded state). Then, 10 μL of analyte was added to each microgel suspension, reaching a final INAT concentration of 10^{-5} M. After 2 h at 4 $^\circ\text{C}$, time enough to reach thermodynamic equilibrium, the samples were excited with the three different laser lines to collect the SERS spectra. Thereafter, the samples were equilibrated at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$ (collapsed state) and the SERS spectra were recorded again. After each equilibration step, spectra were collected under the same conditions. In this first characterization, SERS spectra of INAT were recorded in suspension by using a macrosampling accessory. In the following ultradetection experiments, all of the samples were cast and air-dried onto a glass slide and the 785 laser line was used for the measurements. Ultradetection of petachlorophenol (PCP) was carried out using the same procedure as described in the second experiment (i.e., by magnetic concentration and casting); aliquots (1 mL) of the material diluted 20-fold and with concentration of PCP ranging from 10^{-5} M to 10^{-12} M.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles were prepared using a small variation of a recently reported method, based on the thermal decomposition of Fe(III) acetylacetonate in the presence of undecenoic acid.³³ This method yields particles with an average size around 13 nm, as determined by TEM (Figure 1A). The magnetic properties of as synthesized iron oxide nanoparticles (Figure 1B) are in good agreement with recently reported results,³⁷ showing saturation magnetization close to that of bulk magnetite. The actual saturation magnetization (M_s) values for the present system are 87 ± 2 emu/g at 5K and 76 ± 3 emu/g at 300 K. These magnetic saturation values are particularly high, which reflects the high quality of the material, as compared to usual iron oxide nanoparticles, which are typically much lower due to surface spin disorder.³⁸ This points toward the presence of a solid solution of magnetite and maghemite.³⁹

pNIPAM coating of the magnetic particles was achieved by adding butenoic acid to promote a terminal double bond over the nanoparticles surface, which we have previously used for uniform

polymerization on gold nanorods.³⁴ Encapsulation within pNIPAM shells was then carried out by simply removing excess butenoic acid and CTAB (which was added to avoid the aggregation of the magnetic particles) and mixing with the NIPAM monomer, cross-linker (BIS), and initiator (AAPH). A representative TEM image of the resulting core-shell particles is shown in Figure 2A. It is clear from this image that all the iron oxide nanoparticles are perfectly encapsulated within the pNIPAM shells, which indicates that the vinyl groups present on the surface promote a uniform polymerization that results in the formation of a continuous shell. Silver seeds were then generated inside the pores of the polymer shell by adsorption of silver ions followed by fast in situ reduction using sodium borohydride.⁴⁰ The resulting system shows a well-dispersed collection of small silver nanoparticles inside the entire pNIPAM matrix (Figure 2B). We found however that these particles are not particularly efficient as SERS platforms due to the small Ag particle size and low level of plasmon coupling. Thus, an additional growth step was carried out by adding silver ions from solution and using a mixture of CTAB and glycine to promote the epitaxial deposition of Ag on the preformed seeds.⁴¹ The morphology of the final SERS platform can be seen in Figure 2C, where it is clear that the magnetic particles are concentrated in the center, whereas the grown silver nanoparticles are preferentially close to the shell surface.

UV-vis spectroscopy (Figure 3A) shows a localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) band, with a maximum centered at 421 nm, broader and red-shifted with respect to similar uncoated

Figure 2. Representative TEM images of (A) the encapsulated magnetic nanoparticles after pNIPAM polymerization, (B) the magnetite@pNIPAM nanohybrid materials containing silver seeds, and (C) the final magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM composite microgels.

particles in water, when the polymer is expanded (below 30 °C), which becomes further broadened and red-shifted upon increasing the temperature (over 37 °C) due to the collapse of the pNIPAM shell and subsequent increase in the plasmon coupling when more Ag nanoparticles get closer to each other. This effect has been found to be reversible as previously shown for Au nanorods.^{42,43} The shift is not as remarkable here because of the small silver particle size. The thermosensitive swelling and collapse has been confirmed by dynamic light scattering (DLS), as shown in Figure 3B, which allows identification of a lower critical solution temperature (LCST) around 32 °C, similar to that of the pure microgel. UV-vis was also acquired in the magnetically concentrated material, however the spot was small and black (see optical picture in Figure 4), thus we were unable to obtain any meaningful data. However, the spectrum is not expected to change significantly. It should be noted that LSPR comes from the Ag nanoparticles within the microgels and accumulation on the wall should not affect the morphology of the colloidal composite.

We carried out an initial SERS characterization of the optical enhancing properties of the composite microgel particles, using 1-naphthalenethiol (1NAT) as molecular probe and three excitation laser lines, ranging from the visible to the NIR. The SERS spectra were collected at different temperatures from the colloidal dispersion, so that the swelling and collapse of the microgel would occur normally. For all of the laser lines, the SERS spectra (Figure 4A) show well-defined bands with high intensity, which are characteristic of 1NAT: ring stretching (1553, 1503, and 1368 cm^{-1}), CH bending (1197 cm^{-1}), ring breathing (968 and 822 cm^{-1}), ring deformation (792, 664, 539, and 517 cm^{-1}), and CS stretching (389 cm^{-1}), allowing ultrasensitive detection in a wide spectral window of excitation wavelengths. However, the SERS intensity was found to be temperature dependent, in agreement with the observed changes in the LSPR band. For all of the laser lines, the intensity of the SERS signal consistently increases as the gel collapses (at high temperature). The volume reduction of the material when the temperature is increased drives the embedded silver nanoparticles closer to each other, thus promoting the interaction between their respective electromagnetic fields (plasmon coupling) and leading to further increase of the enhanced Raman signal due to the formation of hot spots. This statement is supported by the significant increase of the signal at high temperature in all cases, but it is more pronounced when the

Figure 3. (A) UV-vis spectra (at temperatures below, gray line, and above, black line, the LCST) of magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM microgels. UV-vis of similar uncoated particles in water is presented for comparison, dotted line. (B) Size dependence of the hydrodynamic diameter of the magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM nanohybrid with temperature.

Figure 4. (A) SERS spectra of 1NAT in magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM in the swollen (4 °C, blue) and collapsed (60 °C, red) states, for different excitation laser lines (532, 633, and 785 nm). (B) Comparison of intensities of the band at 1368 cm^{-1} at low (blue) and high (red) temperature (average intensity and standard deviation for five measurements, green bars). (C) Optical image of the magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM micro gels before and after exposure to a permanent magnet. (D) Detection limits for 1NAT in dilute dispersions of magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM after concentration of the material using a permanent magnet.

laser energy is decreased (toward the IR), ranging from barely 1.2-fold in the case of the green line (532 nm) to over 5-fold increase in the case of the NIR line (785 nm).

For testing the ultrasensitive power of the material, two different experiments were devised. First, aliquots of the composite colloid with concentrations of 1NAT ranging from 10^{-5} M to 10^{-8} M were prepared at 4 °C. After 2 h, 10 μL of each sample were cast onto a glass slide and air-dried (leading to microgel collapse, similar to the effect of temperature increase). In the second experiment, we diluted 20-fold the magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM colloid and then mixed 1 mL aliquots of the dilute colloid with 1NAT concentrations ranging from 10^{-8} M to 10^{-13} M. After 2 h, the magnetic particles were collected at the wall of the vial with a permanent magnet (110 mT) and an iron nail so the magnetic particles are concentrated in a small spot. Carefully, 10 μL of the concentrated spot were cast and air-dried prior to SERS measurements. Whereas the detection limit determined for 1NAT with the original composite microgel was around 10^{-8} M, dilution of the magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM dispersion and subsequent concentration into a small spot with a permanent magnet readily allowed us to decrease the detection limit down to 10^{-12} M, i.e., by 4 orders of magnitude (Figure 4C). Such an improvement is mainly due to a more efficient use of the sensing material; a decrease in the amount of adsorbent (plasmonic material) allows in turn a decrease in the amount of adsorbable (analyte), thereby reaching a sufficient level to be observed in SERS.²⁸ Additionally, the magnetic accumulation of the composite microgel particles effectively increases the amount of material that is actually sampled by the laser beam, thus increasing the amount of scattering centers and the signal reaching the detector.

Figure 5. SERS ultradetection of PCP in dilute dispersions of magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM after concentration of the material in a spot using a permanent magnet. Excitation laser line: 785 nm.

A final experiment was carried out to test the applicability of the prepared material for real applications, which ultimately led to recording the first reported SERS ultrasensitive detection of pentachlorophenol (PCP). On the basis of the previous experiments, we decided to use dilute dispersions of magnetite-Ag@pNIPAM, which were added to certain volumes of PCP with concentrations ranging from 10^{-5} down to 10^{-12} M, at low temperature (4 °C). The temperature was then raised to 60 °C to collapse the microgel, thereby inducing the trapping of PCP molecules within the collapsed microgel,²¹ and finally the particles were concentrated with a permanent magnet into a small spot, where it was analyzed with the Raman spectrometer. The recorded SERS spectra (Figure 5) were found to match band to band the Raman spectrum of pure PCP, but with different relative intensities, as usual in SERS experiments. Briefly, the enhanced vibrational spectrum is dominated by strong peaks at 1554 and 1448 cm^{-1} (ring stretching), 963 cm^{-1} (ring breathing and C–Cl stretching), 761 cm^{-1} (C–Cl stretching), 419 cm^{-1} (OH out of plane deformation), and 396 (out of plane ring deformation),⁴⁴ which are perfectly recognized down to the nanomolar regime. This sensitivity illustrates the capability of SERS to achieve the low detection limits required for PCP (1 ppb; 1 mg L^{-1}), as mandated by EPA^{45,46} and demonstrates that SERS can be used as a general ultrasensitive analytical technique, through careful design and implementation of composite enhancing substrates.

CONCLUSIONS

We have been able to efficiently incorporate optical and magnetic functionalities within microgel spheres, through combination of NIPAM polymerization on the surface of highly magnetic iron oxide nanocrystals and in situ nucleation and growth of silver nanoparticles. Through combination of the thermosensitive properties of the microgel network with the magnetic and optical functionalities of the incorporated nanoparticles, this material can be used to maximize the SERS signal from analyte molecules that are mechanically trapped upon collapse of the pNIPAM microgels. This effect is based on a collective strategy based on the generation of hot spots upon heating, which induces plasmon coupling and hot spot formation, and efficient concentration of the composite particles by simply applying an external magnetic field. Practical application of this material has been demonstrated through the first example of PCP detection based on SERS.

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